

Acadamh Óg na hÉireann
Young Academy Ireland

Narrative CV Toolkit: Resources and Examples

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Introduction and Background

Young Academy Ireland hosted a workshop on narrative CVs in The Royal Irish Academy, Dublin on January 22, 2025. This session explored the benefits of narrative CVs in highlighting diverse skills and achievements beyond traditional metrics. Unlike standard CVs, narrative CVs allow researchers to demonstrate a broader range of skills, experiences, and achievements by putting greater emphasis on qualitative context rather than quantitative markers.

A common Narrative CV format is the *Résumé For Researchers* template, developed by The Royal Society (UK) and structured around four key modules:

- (1) Contributions to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies, or knowledge
- (2) Contributions to the development of others and maintenance of effective working relationships
- (3) Contributions to the wider research and innovation community
- (4) Contributions to supporting broader society and the economy.

This document includes examples of narrative CV snippets to guide researchers in crafting their own impactful narrative CVs in each of these four modules. It also features an exercise at the end to help apply these principles, as well as a curated list of useful resources to support further learning and development.

Examples and CV Snippets

The CV snippets provided here are constructed examples for demonstration purposes only, and do not reflect the range of possible stylistic or formal approaches, personalised perspectives, or career stage-specific materials one can include in their own Narrative CV.

(1) Contributions to the generation of new ideas, tools, methodologies or knowledge

Examples include publications, Masters/PhD theses, exhibitions, hypotheses, book chapters, posters, methods, standards, data or data releases, tools, software, surveys you performed, patents, case reports, excavations, funding/major projects (on-going or completed). These can include roles within teams.

→ Key writing consideration: what technical or intellectual qualifications/experience do you have that makes you best suited for the application?

CV Snippet 1:

My academic journey has centred on the chemistry of dyes, exploring both their historical significance and contemporary applications. During my PhD, awarded in 2015, I developed innovative methods for analysing and synthesizing organic dyes. This work led to two well-cited peer-reviewed publications (81 and 33, according to Google Scholar), offering new insights into the chemical stability and degradation of dye compounds, with implications for heritage science and contemporary dye technologies.

Following my PhD, I joined a large ERC-funded multidisciplinary team investigating dyes in medieval manuscripts. Over three years, I spearheaded the chemical analysis workstream, collaborating closely with historians and conservation scientists. This resulted in a first-author manuscript published in the *Royal Society Letters*, and a book chapter in which I was the sole author (“Colouring the Past”, Chapter 7).

CV Snippet 2:

PhD study: My ongoing PhD research focuses on traditions within English translations of historic and contemporary Turkish horror literature, with a particular focus on cross-cultural narrative adaptation.

Publications: I have published one conference proceedings (“Gorebetçi: Translating the Grotesque in Turkish Horror Literature”), Proceedings of Translating Fear: Cultural Perspectives on Horror Narratives, Cork 2025) and one book chapter (“In The Ağız of Madness”, chapter in “Contemporary Translations”, pg. 17–25). Both publications assess modern trends and interpretations in the translations of Turkish horror literature into English.

(2) Contributions to the development of others and maintenance of effective working relationships

Examples include students you have supervised (secondary school, undergraduate, Masters, PhDs), teaching colleagues to use specific techniques or equipment, workshops you have run or contributed to, postdocs supervised, informal mentorship of more junior PhDs or peers, leading collaborations, team or collaboration membership, teaching (particularly when focused on development e.g. skills), leadership roles or achievements in non-academic settings, or academic teaching. What was your role in all of these, how did you overcome challenges, and what did you together achieve?

→ Key writing consideration: what evidence can you provide of being able to lead a project or team?

CV Snippet 1:

Throughout my career, I have actively supported the development of students, colleagues, and team members. During my PhD, I supervised undergraduate students in practical experiments (CHEM101, CHEM102) and served as a group tutor in “R for Chemists”. In my postdoctoral role, I supervised three Master’s students, guiding them in designing experiments and data interpretation. All three successfully completed their dissertations, with two achieving a publication in peer-reviewed journals.

While working in industry (2019–2020), I led a team of three scientists, mentoring them in project management, technical skills, and professional growth. My leadership emphasized fostering a collaborative and innovative environment, enabling team members to contribute to the successful development of several product lines (JPN Visuals Product #303.1, #312.2, #312.4). I also completed a professional certificate in team development (Oct–Dec 2019), further improving my leadership skills.

CV Snippet 2:

Supervision of interns: In my previous role as Communications Officer in IKEA, I supervised two interns in the Communications office. I was responsible for their training in internal procedures, overseeing their work, and providing informal mentorship to support their professional growth

Volunteer Literacy Coach: Each week, I volunteer as a literacy coach in my local Primary School homework club, Kilcreebh. As a native of Kilcreebh, I am all too aware of the long-standing social challenges in the area and I am committed to supporting local students. I create reading activities, lead storytelling sessions, and organize book drives to engage young readers. My contributions have led me to winning a Community Award in 2022 and 2023.

(3) Contributions to the wider research and innovation community

Examples include peer review, making a slack channel or community for researchers, organizing a seminar series, contributions to open research (e.g. data or code releases), committee work (e.g. within your organization), contributions to inclusivity (e.g. acting as a safety officers, contributing to an Athena Swan committee), conference organization or volunteering, contribution to policy or academic networks (e.g. the National Open Research Forum), having a position of responsibility within your organization.

→ Key writing consideration: what evidence can you give that you contribute to a better research environment and work culture within a field, organization, or network? Examples will depend greatly on career stage.

CV Snippet 1:

I have served as a peer reviewer for journals in conservation science and analytical chemistry (4 publications total).

Currently, I am a member of the science committee for the Analytical Chemistry Conference (ACC 2026), where I have advocated for the increased inclusion of multidisciplinary research. I also act as Secretary on the Equality and Access Committee of the conference, where I gained a lot of experience of what is required to ensure an accessible environment for all participants.

CV Snippet 2:

Journal Club: Since 2023, I have run a journal club within my Department, focusing on global popular literature and academic responses to it. This club has been a success, consistently attracting at least 10 attendees each week.

Graduate Student Representative: I currently serve as the Graduate Student Representative on the School Executive Committee. Although this is a non-voting role, I have been the voice for graduate students' interests on the committee, and successfully petitioned for several changes within the School based on their feedback. These include better kitchen facilities, clearer policies on personal leave, and the creation of a Graduate Development Officer position.

(4) Contributions to supporting broader society and the economy

Examples include public outreach, media coverage or participation, interaction with stakeholders or patient groups, contribution to policy development (governmental, NGO, industrial) development of a patent, commercialization, industrial partnerships, translation of research into industrial/medical applications, public consultation or co-design, blog writing, podcast interviews.

→ Key writing consideration: how have you gotten your work to people who will benefit from it, and what was the impact of this? The specifics will vary greatly from discipline to discipline.

CV Snippet 1:

While my primary contributions have been within academic and industrial settings, I have also made efforts to engage with the public to share the relevance of my work. During my postdoctoral position, I participated in museum outreach events, where I explained the science of medieval dyes to non-specialist audiences (August 2017).

In industry, I collaborated with clients to ensure our UV-sensitive dyes met their needs, bridging the gap between technical research and practical application. This involved a co-design process and led to the production of a UV-B tolerant dye (product code: #AP002.1), which is now used in the roofing of modular housing in high UV regions (see report from Silicon Republic linked below).

CV Snippet 2:

Podcast host: I co-host a podcast called “Chapter, Verse, and Hearse”, which offers accessible discussions about horror literature from diverse cultural contexts. The podcast has over 100 weekly listeners from over 15 countries, and has been featured in a write-up on books.ie.

Public engagement: Building on the reach of my podcast, I am active on social media platforms where I promote little-known books and those originally written in non-English languages. My accounts have over 8,000 followers and I regularly receive positive engagement. This visibility has led to me being invited to speak at two different book festivals (Limerick Literary Festival and the Night Words festival in Berlin, both 2026).

Multilingual and multicultural communications: My PhD thesis, which focuses on English translations of Turkish horror literature, aims to break down and interrogate cross cultural and language barriers. I plan to publish my thesis in a condensed form in English, Turkish, and German, to promote more cross-cultural exchange of literature traditions; I have already published my first chapter in these languages as free and openly accessible documents (doi: dlly32.x).

Other sections seen in CV

Biosketch: *A short introduction of you & your career history – maybe 3-5 sentences depending on the space available or application requirements. This should contextualize you as an individual researcher, covering your research interests and approach. You should consider specifically tailoring this to the current application.*

Example Biosketch: I have built a career that bridges academic research, interdisciplinary collaboration, and industrial innovation, equipping me with the skills and experience to lead a large, ambitious ERC project. During my PhD, I developed novel analytical techniques for dyes, resulting in two highly cited publications that advanced the field. My subsequent transition to industry further demonstrated my leadership abilities, as I managed a team to develop UV-sensitive dyes and secured a patent for a novel formulation. These experiences demonstrate my ability to lead diverse teams, innovate independently, and integrate knowledge across disciplines—skills central to the success of my proposed project.

Key Research Outputs or Achievements: *Many CV formats will allow you to highlight a certain number of research outputs. These should be most relevant to the current application. If possible, provide a brief narrative text describing the relevance of the research output to the current submission e.g. the skills you employed, theoretical developments you produced, specific analyses you contributed, any relevant learnings you acquired which make you a better candidate. Remember, avoid reference to indexes such as Journal Impact Factor or h-index if specified by the organisation you are applying to. Citation number of research output may be allowable depending on the organization you are applying to; consider other ways of indicating the impact of your work.*

Example Key Research Outputs or Achievements: Author lists are provided when below 8 contributors, and abbreviated to the four first and last authors when over 8. My author position is underlined for visual clarity.

1. “Stability and Degradation of Organic Dyes in Humidity Environments,” Journal of Analytical Chemistry (2015), Author X, Author Y, Author Z: This publication has had significant impact (>60 citations), and demonstrated key advances in dye spectrographic analysis. I was responsible for all laboratory work, including the OM spin analysis, which will be the core of Work Package 1. I also co-analysed the data, led the spectrological analyses, and co-wrote the article, including the initial draft.
2. “Revealing Medieval Manuscripts: Advanced Analytical Techniques for Dye Characterization,” Heritage Science (2018), Author X, Author A, Author B: This landmark study (citations: >90) identified a Russian-derived indigo dye in 6th-century British manuscripts, a first in its field. The article garnered media attention and was featured in *New Scientist*. I conducted all the chemical analyses, integrated data from the multidisciplinary team, and co-wrote the article. This work led me to being invited to present at the Medieval Manuscripts of the Atlantic workshop (January 2020), and has been instrumental in developing the collaborative network required for this proposed project. This has also provided me with experience in leading large multi-disciplinary teams, an important skill for conducting groundbreaking research.

Career breaks, diverse career paths and major life events: *These sections provide additional context to your career trajectory and achievements. Pay close attention to what is allowed in this section by the organization you are applying to. This may be the section to contextualize apparent “gaps” in your CV, for example due to Carer’s Leave, Parental Leave, or if you have been affected by toxic work environments. Not everyone will have text to put in a section like this, but many will.*

Example Career breaks, diverse career paths and major life events: In 2018, I took a six-month maternity leave, temporarily stepping away from academic research. Following this, I decided to transition from academia to industry, where I successfully applied my skills to address commercial challenges at ChemX (2018–2021). Although I did not publish peer-reviewed articles during this period, I led the development of three patents (detailed provided elsewhere).

Exercise

Imagine you are applying for your next dream project or job. What are the three top achievements or outputs that make you the ideal candidate? If you don't have three specific achievements or outputs, what key skills or experiences position you as the best person for the project or job? How did you acquire those skills? Why do they make you the strongest candidate? In short, what is your elevator pitch for yourself as a researcher?

1)

2)

3)

Resources

Below is a list of valuable resources and guides for creating narrative CVs, as well as examples and templates used by various organizations and funding bodies:

1. **[List of DORA Signatories](#)**
Includes major organizations such as the European Commission, Science Foundation Ireland (SFI), Irish Research Council (IRC), Health Research Board (HRB), Wellcome Trust, and The Royal Society (UK).
2. **[University of Glasgow Narrative CV Project](#)**
A resourceful project offering insights on narrative CVs under a Creative Commons CC_BY 4.0 license.
3. **[University of Oxford Narrative CV Guide](#)**
This guide provides a detailed framework, with useful template sentences and examples. Licensed under Creative Commons Attribution 4.0 International.
4. **[University of Dundee “Writing a Narrative CV” Guide](#)**
A concise guide on writing a narrative CV, under a Creative Commons CC BY-NC-ND license.
5. **[PEPCV Platform](#)**
A platform designed for obtaining feedback on narrative CVs, featuring an excellent series of videos on how to create effective narrative CVs.
6. **[SFI \(Research Ireland\) Narrative CV Format](#)**
Official narrative CV guidelines provided by Research Ireland (formerly SFI).
7. **[ERC Starter Grant CV](#)**
Part of the ERC B1 application process, tailored for early-stage researchers.
8. **[MSCA CV Format](#)**
Guidance for preparing CVs as part of the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions (MSCA).
9. **Résumé for Research and Innovation (R4RI) - UKRI**
 - o **[Template](#)**: Official R4RI template for researchers.
 - o **[Context](#)**: Background information on the R4RI framework.
10. **Wellcome Trust Narrative CV**
 - o CV details are provided through their online system.
 - o Includes a career break section but does not require personal details or reasons.
 - o Based on the “Resumé for Researchers” 4-section template.
 - o Includes a detailed CV section for reference.